

EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES FOR VISUALIZATION OF ROCK-CUT SANCTUARY NEAR THE VILLAGE OF BABYAK, BULGARIA

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Various non-traditional forms and methods are gaining popularity in the contemporary presentation of cultural heritage. Such innovative forms of presentation are projection displays, interactive 2D and 3D, multi-touch displays, games and applications for mobile devices, virtual reality, augmented reality and mixed reality technologies.

Before the digital era one of the most interesting ways of reviving the past and culture of ancient societies was the historical reenactment. The organization of this type of activity is a complex process and requires the involvement of many people, the commitment of a solid management and organizational resource. It requires significant funds for acquisition and production of authentic requisites and inventory, which in turn creates problems for its storage and maintenance, as well as logistical difficulties in organizing an event. Historical reenactments give us a good idea of the clothing of people in the past; they can also be used to illustrate military equipment, rituals, and other forms of human activity of the past, but we cannot speak of a complete transfer to another reality as with the emerging digital technologies. No matter how well organized the restoration is, even if it is made in the ruins of an ancient city, the viewer can hardly be abstracted from the surrounding

contemporary environment. However rich the imagination may be, it is difficult to not see the ruins and imagine some form of grandeur. This is even more true when presenting cultures and societies from Prehistoric and Thracian times. Often, they are misunderstood and uninteresting to the viewer, but they contain a great potential and many interesting facts about human history, science and knowledge, which in the past were inextricably linked to superstition, magic, religion and myths.

In such a plan, one of the most interesting objects for the modern man, and at the same time the most complex to present, interpret and visualize, are the shrines, sanctuaries, places of worship, proto-temples of ancient societies. Nevertheless, we have a number of good examples of exhibiting such facilities, many of which date back to the Neolithic and Bronze Age. Good examples of exhibiting prehistoric facilities are the museums presenting megalithic temples in Malta, part of the UNESCO World Heritage List¹, the Newgrange tomb as part of the Brú na Bóinne archaeological site in Ireland² and many others.

Modern practices in visualization of cultural heritage.

Emerging digital technologies play a key role in the sustainable preservation and presentation of cultural heritage to different audiences. The modern technologies generate value in many sectors that contribute to the creative economy (*Ch'ng et al.* 2019: 170-180). Suitable way to approach the adoption of modern technologies is to improve the visitor's experience,

¹ <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/132/> (accessed 29.02.2020)

² <http://www.worldheritageireland.ie/bru-na-boinne/> (accessed 29.02.2020)

while creating practical benefits which include improving efficiency and generating revenue (*Cranmer 2017: 347*).

One of the biggest sectors within the creative cultural industry is the museum sector where major cultural artefacts and histories are curated and contextualized (*Ch'ng et al. 2019: 170-180*). Museums try to use digital technologies for many years as supporting tools in their exhibitions and as another marketing instrument for attracting audience.

Digital systems used in museums:

- digital restorations - the digital restoration is similar to the mechanical or chemical restoration, but without any risk to the artifact, because the processing is made on a digital copy (*Arora et al. 2012*). Digital restoration is useful for restoring the conceptual and artistic integrity of complex objects, such as monuments, that were once considered a single entity but are now disassembled and distributed among museums across various nations. It also serves the purpose of protecting archaeological goods from future risks. (*Stanco, Tanasi 2011*);
- projection displays - displays that tell a story and are more than just a picture or a movie;
- interactive 2D - multimedia systems from the 1990s with touch displays;
- multitouch 2D - this includes multi-user, multi-touch displays which support at least two users interacting together;
- interactive 3D – video game environments or simulations which can be operated with an input device like computer mouse or touch screen;
- virtual reality (VR) - any display which completely immerses a user into a virtual world (e.g., headsets), this includes

360 videos. A person utilizing specific electronic equipment, such as a helmet with a screen inside or gloves with sensors, can interact with a computer-generated simulation of a three-dimensional image or scene in a way that appears real or tangible (McMillan *et al.* 2017);

- augmented reality (AR) - any gadgets (like HoloLens) that superimpose virtual images onto the physical world through the use of QR codes, photos, or spaces. (Ch'ng *et al.* 2019: 170-180);

Remote presentation of heritage sites. The remote presentation through Internet is usable when the consumers of cultural products do not have the ability to attend personally on the place of interest, especially when it is located in a distant and difficult to reach area. This type of presentation is suitable for people with disabilities, senior adults and little children. The technologies used for this kind of entertainment are mobile applications, games, VR enabled computer simulations, remotely piloted robotic alter ego³.

On-site visualization of cultural heritage. When tourists visit a heritage site, they expect to see something impressive. They want to hear interesting story about the monument and they even want to be totally immersed in the history and atmosphere of ancient times. This is not completely possible with the classical means used by museums and there is a need of new methods for visualization and exhibition of ancient architecture

³ <https://www.braincontrol.com/en/braincontrol-avatar-in-anteprima-mondiale-al-museo-del-santa-maria-della-scala-di-siena-per-le-visite-da-remoto/> (accessed 29.02.2020)

and cultural artifacts. Some of the new methods that use emerging technologies include:

- holograms – the hologram may be described as an apparition of something that seems tangible, but in an empty space. Something that does not exist but appears as if it was real, an optical illusion. Through holograms we do not immerse ourselves in virtual reality, but it is the virtual reality that enters our space. Our reality becomes an augmented reality (*Pietroni et al.* 2019). There are different types of holographic technologies and some of them have been invented many years ago. The holography itself has many limitations for using outdoors, but there are holographic projection methods, which are suitable for bigger images and outdoor presentations.

- augmented reality – it is used for displaying images of objects, buildings, people and events in the same place where they originally appeared. This technology augments virtual images using the reality as a background making the scenes more realistic and easier to be perceived by the viewer. Recent advancements have expanded the use of augmented reality beyond conventional hand-held or eye-worn displays, opening up new application domains. Large spatially-aligned optical components like video projectors and mirror beam combiners, transparent screens, or holograms are used. This technology is known as spatial augmented reality (SAR). (*Bimber, Raskar* 2005).

- spatial augmented reality (projection mapping or video mapping) – this is a 3D video projection technology for displaying images on real non-flat objects with the purpose of

creating realistic perception and immersing the viewer into the visual storytelling⁴.

These visualization technologies for cultural heritage sites require appropriate images and scans to be made and processed. The form, dimensions, and outward appearance of cultural heritage sites and objects can be captured using a variety of geotechnologies, including mobile LiDAR systems (MLS), aerial and terrestrial photogrammetry, airborne and terrestrial laser scanning, global navigation satellite systems (*Di Angelo et al.* 2019). After that computer generated images (CGI) can be created and these images may serve as a base for projecting historical scenes or artifacts in a museum or on-site environment. CGI can be used also for programming virtual spaces for applications or games.

An augmented reality (AR) system adds virtual, or computer-generated, images to the real environment so they seem to reside in the same space. An AR system has the following characteristics: operates interactively and in real time, integrates real and virtual objects in a single environment by aligning all the objects (*Azuma et al.* 2001: 34-47). The difference between VR and AR is that rather than immersing a person into a completely synthetic world, AR attempts to embed synthetic supplements into the real environment (or into a live video of the real environment) (*Bimber, Raskar* 2005). AR platforms have their limitations – while they can add virtual content to unknown real environment, they cannot recognize the

⁴ <http://projection-mapping.org/the-history-of-projection-mapping/>
(accessed 29.02.2020)

semantic meaning of real-world objects. That's why most consumer AR applications use the real world just as a background for the augmentations. Today the most important question is whether or not a usage of AR makes a meaningful connection to the real world (Azuma 2019: 26-32).

Tourist organizations should explore the use of AR as a method of attracting audiences, increasing visitors' numbers and encouraging more sustainable year-round visitor flow. Likewise, organizations should consider integrating AR to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of educating their visitors to improve learning. Such as introducing AR animations or overlays on existing displays to demonstrate complex processes. Importantly, it is recommended that adopting AR could create new employment opportunities and improve the demand for local services (Cranmer 2017).

Mixed/merged reality, or MR, refers to the blending of the actual and virtual worlds to create new settings and visualizations in which real-time interactions occur between digital and physical items. Mixed reality is a combination of reality and virtual reality that exists in both the real and virtual worlds. (McMillan, Glaeser 2017; 162-168).

The rock-cut sanctuary of Babyak as a model for visualization using emerging technologies.

Augmented reality and other emerging technologies can help the distant heritage sites to connect with their audience. To illustrate this process as closely as possible, we have selected one of the most difficult to socialize monuments known as rock-cut sanctuaries. This type of monuments has always been a problem with accessibility. Many of them are in inaccessible areas. They

serve as examples of significant monuments that have been thoroughly researched, but after a brief moment of glory they fall into oblivion again. One of the well-researched sites of this type is the rock-cut sanctuary at Peak Babyak near the village of Babyak in the Western Rhodopes Mountain, Bulgaria.

Peak Babyak, “Babyashka chuka” or “Babyashka mogila” is the dominant hill in the westernmost part of the Rhodope Mountains. During the construction of the television tower, fragments of votive tiles, studied by Lyuba Ognenova, are located on it. The images on them are interpreted as a pair of Thracian deities, visually identical with the Greek Zeus and Hera, and on one of the tiles the image is interpreted as Bendida-Hera (*Ognenova 1959: 82-93*). The findings in question indicate that there was a sanctuary at the top. The site is located at an altitude of 1656m and offers a view of the whole Razlog valley, as well as the slopes of Pirin, Rila and Western Rhodopes (*Genov 2018: 124*). This in turn determines good visual connections with other cult sites localized in these areas (*Gotsev, Tonkova 2008: 32*). The Babyak peak sanctuary became the object of study again in 1983 by Mieczyslaw Domaradzki, and the research was continued by his team in the person of Alexei Gotsev and Milena Tonkova. Archaeologists Ilia Kulov and Rumen Mikov also participate in separate campaigns (*Gotsev, Tonkova 2008: 30*). The systematic long-term studies of the sanctuary make it one of the most significant archeological sites providing information about the role and function of mountain sanctuaries in Thrace.

According to Ognenova's original views, the sanctuary was in operation from the end of the Bronze Age to the 4th century AD (*Ognenova 1959: 88*). In later studies by Domaradzki and his

team the date is confirmed (*Gotsev, Tonkova* 2008: 190). An important testimony to the nature of the faith and its connection to the rite of worship is the fact that initially the peak was entirely rocky, with the earth's layer being the result of the accumulation of cult activity. The long period of peak use, about 1500 years, causes significant cultural stratification. In places, the cultural layer reaches a thickness of 3 meters (*Gotsev, Tonkova* 2008: 32). Another characteristic feature of the sanctuary related to its geomorphology is that two elevations connected with a saddle can be distinguished at the summit (*Genov* 2018: 125).

Interesting objects for digital restoration and visual representation are the ritual fireplaces called “*eschara*”, meaning sacrificial hearth, altar. They could be revived by creating and displaying scenes of giving gifts to gods. Interesting ritual is the pouring of liquid (wine) in the fire. Information about this ritual is collected from the votive offerings representing female deity found on the site. Probably this is one of the worshipped deities in this sanctuary. The goddess is represented as holding a patera or phiale. This container is used for pouring wine on the sacrificial altar. All of these images could come to life by using 3D projection mapping, holography and augmented reality. 3D videos, which represent the sanctuary from its establishment to its decline, can be created and displayed at the sanctuary.

Positive factor for the development of this heritage site is its geographic location. The Babyak peak is visible from the whole valley of Razlog when the sky is clear. It needs appropriate publicity, infrastructure and modern program for tourists to become an attractive entertainment center. The sanctuary of Babyak is located near the big ski resort Bansko, which makes it

potentially alternative tourist destination attracting tourists who seek to discover ancient cultural heritage.

To summarize the characteristics of the Babyak sanctuary, we created a table with its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats and then put them together with the possible changes in these characteristics after creating and applying a new visual representation using emerging technologies.

Table 1. SWOT analysis of current state of the heritage site and possible future results after using modern technologies

	Before	After
Strengths	Easy management, no expenses	Accessibility, good conservation, authentic interpretation, attracting young visitors
Weaknesses	Lack of accessibility	Expensive maintenance
Opportunities	Potential for scientific research	Developing local economy and cultural tourism
Threats	Oblivion, no revenue for local community	Loss of authenticity

As we can see from the table some of the problems of rock-cut sanctuaries and their socialization could be overcome by

accepting and using modern methods of visualization such as augmented reality and mixed reality.

The development and promotion of a cultural site, such as the rock-cut sanctuary near Babyak, could be the first step for representing the regional cultural heritage to the public and for thinking about it as a treasury for the community. The big advantage of the emerging technologies is that they are nondestructive and using them avoids conflicts between municipal authorities, tour agencies and environmental organizations. There is a need for careful risk assessment because the threats of losing authenticity and environmental changes are real. Nevertheless, positive factors for the region prevail and negatives should be adequately controlled and minimized.

Conclusion.

Thinking globally, emerging technologies combined with cultural heritage can be used for education - teachers can show children and their families the history of a place in an attractive and informative way. Young people can be involved in preserving the historical monuments and significant places by interactive learning and gamification. Companies can develop commercial applications and promotional campaigns for cultural tourism which brings added value for local communities. Cultural tourism could improve social interaction between people sharing the same interests (*Allan, Altal* 2016: 43-50). Heritage tourism and significance provide an opportunity to create a positive image for the area and improve national identity, while for locals it can create a way to satisfy personal needs and motivations (*Greffe* 2004: 301-309). This may lead to developing local business and economy growth.

REFERENCES

Allan, M.; Altal, Y. 2016 *Museums and tourism: Visitors motivations and emotional involvement*. Med. Archaeol. Archaeometry, 16, 43–50.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160948>

Arora, N, Kumar, A and Kalra, P. 2012 *Digital restoration of old paintings*. In: International Conference in Central Europe on Computer Graphics, Visualization and Computer Vision (WSCG)

Azuma, R., Baillot, Y., Behringer, R., Feiner, S., Julier, S. and MacIntyre, B. 2001 *Recent advances in Augmented Reality*. IEEE Computer Graphics & Applications.;21 (6), 34-47.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/38.963459>

Azuma, R.T. 2019 *The road to ubiquitous consumer augmented reality systems*. Hum Behav & Emerg Tech. 1:26-32.

Bimber, O., Raskar, R. 2005 *Spatial Augmented Reality*. New York: A K Peters/CRC Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1201/b10624>

Bimber, O., Raskar, R. 2005 *Spatial Augmented Reality*. New York: A K Peters/CRC Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1201/b10624>

Ch'ng, E., Cai, S., Leow, F., and Zhang, T.E. 2019 *Adoption and use of emerging cultural technologies in China's museums*. Journal of Cultural Heritage. 37:170-180.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2018.11.016>

Cranmer, E. 2017 *Developing an augmented reality business model for cultural heritage tourism: the case of Geevor Museum*. Doctoral thesis (PhD), Manchester Metropolitan University.

<https://e-space.mmu.ac.uk/id/eprint/620825>

Di Angelo L, Di Stefano P, Guardiani E, Morabito AE and Pane C. 2019 *3D Virtual Reconstruction of the Ancient Roman Incile of the Fucino Lake*. Sensors.; 19(16):3505.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/s19163505>

Genov, A. 2018 *Obozhestvenata priroda – skalni svetilishta ot Rila, Rodopite i Pirin*. [Deified nature - rock sanctuaries from Rila, Rhodopes and Pirin] Faber